

FOUNDATIONAL SKILLS ASSESSMENT TOOLKIT FOR PRIMARY CLASSES

¹ Rosy Jain (Chitkara College of Education, Chitkara University, Punjab)
² Manu Chadha (GHG Khalsa College of Education, Gurusar Sadhar, Punjab)
³ Parul Sood (Chitkara College of Education, Chitkara University, Punjab)

Email ID: ¹ principalrosyjain@gmail.com

² parul.sood@chitkara.edu.in

³ manumehar@gmail.com

Email ID of the Corresponding author: principalrosyjain@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

5227

Assessing the learning gaps is one of the most important aspect of the teaching-learning process, as it helps to plan differential instructions to cater to the differential needs of students. Nearly five crore children in elementary schools do not have Literacy and Numeracy skills (Draft NEP,2019). Traditional paper pen tests tell us what students did not answer but do not tell specifically the learning areas which need attention. This paper endeavours to design a standardized, simple, cost-effective, and easy-to-administer screening toolkit to assess all four skills, i.e. Listening, Speaking, Writing, and Reading. Items in the tool are designed after considering the expectations of academicians and practitioners in the field of English subject teaching. Then the toolkit was used in a private school as a pilot study, and after item analysis, seven tasks were chosen for the toolkit. Reliability of the toolkit was found using the test-retest method, and it was 0.92. Content validity and construct validity of the toolkit was also established.

KEYWORDS: Foundational skills, basic skills, Literacy skills, Screening toolkit, Diagnostic test

DOI Number: 10.14704/nq.2022.20.10.NQ55500

NeuroQuantology 2022;20(10):5227-5239

INTRODUCTION

Foundational Literacy skills refer to the skills and strategies involved in Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing. If students have mastered these foundational skills, no one can stop them from being lifelong learners and successful in life. Now the question arises, "Are we really able to impart foundational skills amongst the students?" Only 27.2% of grade III students can read a grade II level text, and 25% of children leaving grade VIII cannot read a grade II level

text (Aser, 2018). According to PISA's (Programme for International Student Assessment) international competency-based assessment, India is ranked 72nd amongst 74 countries. This indicates that India needs to work hard to match international standards.

The world is passing through the 'global learning crisis' (USAID, 2016; UNESCO, 2013). It is seen that school children lack basic literacy skills, even after completing their primary education (World Bank, 2018). Reading with

comprehension is one of the essential receptive skills, as the knowledge received via Reading can be expressed in speaking and writing. According to Catherine Snow, " Every other initiative that leader might undertake is less important than making sure that the students in school learn how to read". Literacy is found to be one of the strongest predictors of academics success. A student struggling with Reading generally struggles in all subjects throughout schooling. Therefore, most of the items of the assessment toolkit are designed to assess the students' Reading literacy.

PISA defines Reading literacy in a holistic manner. It considers reading as an interactive process between the reader and the text, not mere decoding or knowledge of vocabulary. Reading literacy is the active, conscious, and useful utilization of Reading in a variety of situations and for a wide range of purposes (OECD, 2019). A fluent reader is one who can read the text for understanding with ease and efficiency (OECD, 2019). Fluency improves comprehension skills because fluent Reading frees up memory and attention, required for higher-order thinking skills like comprehension. Comprehension skill is the ability of an individual to decode words correctly and automatically and understand their meaning to make sense of the text while reading. Information processing strategies, the reader's behavioural aspects, and relevant metacognitive strategies need to be emphasized in order to improve the comprehension skills. Cognitive skills, use of strategies, and motivations to read are required to be assessed in reading assessment.

It is observed that students lack comprehension skills in Indian classrooms (Menon et al., 2017; Sinha, 2012). Reading comprehension is not prioritised in language instruction in India, where the focus is on decoding at a basic level.

As a result, students rely heavily on their teachers to interpret literature for meaning since they find it hard to comprehend. (Narasimhan 2004; Matrija 2006; Sinha 1985). That is because comprehension is assessed but never taught (Menon et al., 2017). This lack of comprehension is the most significant shortcoming as a student is not proficient in comprehending the text independently. If a student cannot construct meaning out of Reading, then it is a futile exercise. Reading comprehension is a combination of effective decoding, vocabulary, word knowledge, comprehension strategies, and monitoring. Decoding alone will not ensure that students understand the meaning of what they are Reading (Michael Pressley 2001). Unless they cannot comprehend the text they read, they cannot be lifelong learners, which is the foremost requirement of education. Therefore, among early learners, comprehension instructions must be provided along with the letter-sound knowledge (Duke and Pearson 2001).

5228

Early screening can help the teachers to understand the differential learning needs of students, that sometimes school's structure and processes fail to identify. Providing differential instructions to students to satisfy their learning needs requires teachers to monitor students' current level of academic progress. Students undergo various paper pen tests during their academic year. Most of these tests are conducted to evaluate their learning. However, in most situations these tests fail to clearly depict the child's current knowledge and skills. Poor scores are not an indication of the child's knowledge. Sometimes students fail to give answers due to a lack of understanding of the questions or maybe due to poor reading skills, they may even fail to read the questions. Even National Policy 2020 looks forward to bringing a

paradigm shift from testing rote memorization to competency-based learning. Hence, there is a need for a Screening toolkit which can correctly pinpoint the areas that require attention to bridge the learning gaps. Therefore, the researcher felt the need to develop a toolkit to assess students' receptive skills in language development (Reading and Listening) to have productive skills (Speaking and Writing). While designing a toolkit that assesses the student's learning gap, the designer should know what to expect from the student. The researcher thus consulted with the children's subject teachers to determine what learning outcomes they were expecting for from the grade III students in terms of grade level and age. This toolkit will provide more detailed or fine-grained information about student learning progress, help the teachers identify the skills that students have mastered and throw light on specific areas where they need improvement.

Construction of the Toolkit

Objectives

To construct and standardize a screening toolkit for grade III to assess students' proficiency level for the Foundational Skills in English Literacy.

Development and standardization of the toolkit

The researcher has gone through the latest assessment trend and studied the toolkit EGRA (Early Grade Reading Assessment) developed by USAID (United States Agency International Development) and EGRA in India. The Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) is administered orally on a one-to-one basis and measures the essential foundational skills for English literacy acquired by early graders. The researcher has gone through the guidelines issued by Nipun Bharat for Foundational Language and Literacy skills and found students should master in following components:-

- **Oral Language Development:** the student should be able to read fluently with

comprehension and should be able to express his/her ideas orally.

- **Phonological Awareness:** Students should be able to work with sounds in spoken language. Child development is phonological before the beginning of formal schooling and continues through third grade and beyond.

- **Decoding:** child showcase the competencies of print awareness, alphabetical knowledge and decoding, and word recognition.

- **Vocabulary:** the child is competent in oral vocabulary, reading/writing vocabulary, and morphological analysis of words.

- **Reading Comprehension:** The child's ability to understand and interpret the text.

- **Reading Fluency:** Ability to read a text with accuracy, speed (automaticity), expression (prosody), and comprehension that allows children to make meaning from the text.

- **Concept about Print:** Children should be exposed to different types of print-rich environments to develop the skill of comprehension.

- **Writing:** This area includes the competencies of writing alphabets and words and writing for expression.

- **Culture of Reading/Inclination towards Reading:** Involves the motivation to engage with various books and other reading material.

The researcher consulted with various academicians and practitioners in the field of education and outlined the expected grade-level learning outcomes. Following those outcomes, a toolkit comprising instruments based on Foundational Skills in English Literacy was designed. Finally, the designed toolkit was sent for the expert opinion of five educators, and amendments were made based on their recommendations. Now the toolkit was ready for the pilot study.

Target Population :

This toolkit is meant for Indian students studying in grade 3.

Sample: A pilot study is being done on 30 students studying in a local school.

READING TOOLKIT FRAMEWORK

Task 1A, 1B, 2 and 6 of the toolkit test the reading skills with fluency, understanding and correct pronunciation as Reading is found to be one of the strongest predictors of academic success. It is found that students struggling with Reading generally continue to struggle in all subjects throughout school. So every initiative the school leader takes is less important than ensuring students learn how to read. (Catherine Snow).

Task 1A comprises a reading snapshot; students would be asked to read a paragraph of 65 words. The paragraph contained 95% of the words which are used in their textbook frequently. However, 5% of words are unfamiliar, and students must apply their decoding skills to read and understand them.

1. SNAPSHOT OF THE TOOLKIT

1.1. Snapshot of the Screening Toolkit for English Literacy for class 3rd

Then the paragraph would be removed for task 1B, and students would be asked to answer five questions based on their understanding of the given text.

Task 2 will assess the students reading based on the given visual. First, students will observe the visual for 1 minute and read carefully and silently. Then, the visual will be removed, and they will be asked to answer based on the visual observed.

Task 6 will assess the students, pronunciation skills and knowledge of silent words.

Task 3 of the toolkit assesses the students' focused listening as they have to draw the figure while following the instructions.

Tasks 4 and 5 are meant to track students' writing skills with accuracy.

Tasks 7 and 8 test students' speaking skills, as they have to speak for 2 minutes on a given topic and for 1 minute describing the prop.

TASK	DESCRIPTION	TIME TAKEN	MARKS	SKILL DEMONSTRATED BY STUDENTS
Subtask 1A Reading with fluency	Reading fluency is determined by calculating the number of words read accurately per minute using the stopwatch.	60 seconds will be provided for Reading	> 53 -65 words read correctly would get five marks > 40-52 words read correctly would get four marks > 27-39 words read correctly would get three marks > 13-26 words read correctly would get two marks > Below 13 words read correctly would get one mark	Students read without error with the correct pronunciation .
Subtask 1B comprehension	The child will be asked to read the passage once again without a stopwatch completely then the five oral questions will be answered by the		1 mark = correct response 0 mark = incorrect response X= no response	Students should read the passage with understanding

	student without referring to the passage to check the understanding level the child.	-		
2. Reading visuals(advertisement) with understanding	Five questions would be asked based on shown advertisement	One minute for the observation. 2 minutes for the questions	1 mark = correct response 0 mark = incorrect response X= no response	Students understanding Reading of the visual
3. Listening	The child has to follow the instructions and draw the figure.	-	Five marks based on instructions followed	Focused listening
4. Writing Skills	The child will be given a picture to describe	-	Five marks depend upon spellings, punctuation, content, grammar and Cohesion.	Writing with accuracy
5. Dictation	A short paragraph of 70-80 words would be read by the assessor first. Students will listen without writing. Students will write the passage read out by the assessor for the second time.	-	Five marks depend on spellings, punctuation, and capitalization.	Active listening and writing with accuracy
6. Pronunciation	Ten words with the silent letter would be given, and the child has to read correctly within 1 minute.		One mark for each correct pronounced word	Reading the words containing the silent letter correctly.
7. Speaking	The child has to speak for 2 minutes on the topic given by the assessor	2 minutes for thinking. 2 minutes for speaking	Ten marks based on their fluency,correct pronunciation,vocabulary used, and grammar	Expressing verbally with confidence
8. Describing with prop	The child has to speak a few sentences based on the prop given by the assessor	1 minute for thinking 1 minute for speaking	Five marks based on their fluency, correct pronunciation,vocabulary used and grammar	Speaking Skills

Implementation

The toolkit would be implemented by the researcher by keeping the following cautions in mind.

- ❖ The researcher will conduct a Repo building session with the students before carrying out the assessment.
- ❖ The researcher will make students feel comfortable and will take them into confidence by saying that it will not impact their academic results and enjoy it like a game.
- ❖ The researcher would have the clear-cut purpose of implementation of the tool.
- ❖ The researcher will carry a stopwatch, assessment sheets already copied according to the number of students and, according to the task required, blank sheets, a pen, pencil, and eraser.
- ❖ To carry out the Reading task, the researcher will have two copies of the same paragraph. One copy will be provided to the student to read, and the second will be retained by the assessor. When the child is reading the paragraph, the researcher will underline the misspelt words at the same time and note down the time using a stopwatch. After 1 minute assessor will tell him to stop their Reading and would mark till the paragraph is read. Now the assessor will be able to find out the number of words read per minute correctly. The researcher will give time to reread the paragraph. When the child has read the paragraph completely, the paragraph will be removed. Now the questions would be asked to check the understanding of the child.
- ❖ An advertisement of Parle –G will be shown to the child and instructed to see the picture carefully as five questions based on it would be asked. The child will be allowed to see the picture for one minute, and then the

picture will be removed. Then the assessor will ask the questions. It will check the child's observation and how actively he can retrieve the information from the shown picture to answer the questions.

- ❖ The assessor will provide a blank sheet to the child and asked to draw as per the instructions given.
- ❖ For the writing task, a visual would be shown, and the child would be asked to describe the picture.
- ❖ For dictation, the assessor will keep in mind the age and grade of the students. So he will speak at a slow speed. Instructions would be clearly given. The first-time student will listen to the paragraph read by the assessor. The second time, the assessor will repeat the whole paragraph by repeating a single line two times and ask the students to write.

Pilot Study and Administration of the Tool:

The researcher approached the principals of the local school and got permission to conduct the pilot study in the local school. It was applied to 30 students in grade 3 studying at that school.

In this tool, fidelity is the most crucial factor. Two teachers in each class teaching the subject were trained to carry out the administration of the tool. The training was held for 2 hours for each subject, and then the teacher was asked to act as an assessor.

After designing, it was sent for expert opinion, and it was modified as per their advice. The tool was tried out on 30 students of class 3rd in a local school.

Tryout of the Toolkit

The researcher approached the Principle of the Private school in the Ludhiana district and got permission to conduct the pilot study in the school. The purpose of the pilot study was communicated to assessors and the Principal.

The study was conducted on 30 students studying class 3 in a private school in the Ludhiana district. Required copies of the draft tool for conducting the pilot study were printed, and confidentiality was ensured.

ITEM ANALYSIS:

In order to select the appropriate items for the final draft of the toolkit, it was necessary to obtain the Discriminating Power (D.P.) and Difficulty Value(D.V.) of the tasks to be included in the toolkit finally.

Discriminating Power (D.P.) was calculated by applying the formula

$$D.P. = \frac{R_2 - R_1}{N/2}$$

For computing the Difficulty Value (D.V.), the formula mentioned ahead was used

$$D.V. = \frac{R_2 - R_1}{N}$$

Where R_2 = number of responses of the 27% of the highest performing students.

R_1 = number of responses of 27% of the lowest-performing students.

N = sum total number of both groups.

Kelley's method of item analysis was used to findout the Discriminating Power (D.P.) and Difficulty Value of the tasks of the toolkit.

Kelley (1939) has shown that if we take into consideration the highest performing group of 27% of the total sample, we can confidently say that the highest performing groups have better capability in the skills of a toolkit than the lowest-performing group.

Class 3rd English Literacy

	D.P.	DV	
Task 1 A	0.15625	0.078125	Merge
Task 1 B	0.453125	0.226563	
Task 2	0.390625	0.195313	
Task 3	0.203125	0.101563	Cancelled
Task 4	0.296875	0.148438	Reconstructed
Task 5	0.328125	0.164063	
Task 6	0.726563	0.363281	
Task 7	0.398438	0.199219	
Task 8	0.5625	0.28125	
Task 9	0.210938	0.105469	Cancelled

The final draft of the tool

	D.P.	DV	
Task 1	0.5	0.25	
Task 2	0.675	0.3375	

Task 3	0.475	0.2375	Selected
Task 4	0.625	0.3125	
Task 5	0.58125	0.290625	Selected
Task 6	0.6375	0.31875	Selected
Task 7	0.5125	0.2565	Selected

Reliability

Cronbach’s alpha is widely used to measure the internal consistency of a test. It may not be the most appropriate to measure the reliability of those subtasks that are time-limited. Therefore it cant be used for this screening tool. However, inter-rater reliability (IRR) can be used for the same. So two assessors were appointed to work in a pair to carry out the assessment. One assessor was administrating the assessment, and the other simply listened and scored independently.

The test-retest method is being used to find out the internal consistency of the test. The reliability coefficient can range from a low of zero (negative values are considered zero) to a high of 1.00. In this study, the test-retest method was used to find out the interval consistency of the toolkit. A preliminary draft of the toolkit with nine tasks was conducted twice on 30 students of grade 3 after a gap of 15 days. The correlation between both test scores was found by using Pearson's product-moment correlation formula. English Literacy for class 3rd was found at .92, which indicates that the test is reliable.

Validity

Content validity was established by the opinion of 5 experts. They found the toolkit is designed appropriately, considering all aspects of literacy as per their grade and age. The toolkit does not drift from the operational definition of the purpose of the study. Construct validity was found by consulting ten experts related to the fields. They found that the toolkit measures the skills/abilities that should be measured.

Scoring Procedure

Three types of scoring are being done.

- ❖ **Subscoring:-** Reading subsets in English reading are timed, and students are given 60 seconds to generate responses. These subsets are typically scored as a number of correct words read per minute and are calculated using the following equation:

$$NCPM = \frac{c \times 60}{t}$$

Where: NCPM is the number correct per minute.

c is the number of correct responses
 t is the elapsed time in seconds taken by the student.

This equation takes into consideration students who finish the reading task in less than 60 seconds. For instant, in the pilot study reading passage was 65 words, and a student read the whole passage in 30 seconds, which means their reading speed was 130 words per minute accurately.

seconds to generate responses. These subsets are typically scored as a number of correct words read per minute and are calculated using the following equation:

Writing and speaking items are constructed-response items. Students are supposed to construct their responses and are evaluated using scoring Rubrics. Writing subtask is marked on the basis of spellings, punctuation, capitalization, grammar and content used. Speaking subtask is marked on the basis of their fluency, correct pronunciation, the vocabulary used and grammar.

- ❖ **Composite scoring:** - Composite scores represent aggregated student

performance across significant components of the construct and, as such, are similar to subscores (Sinharay, Haberman, & Puhan, 2007). Reading with comprehension is the combination of two subtasks.

The child is supposed to read the paragraph of 65 words in 1 minute in subtask number 1 and has to answer five questions based on the paragraph

read in subtask 1 A. composite scores of both represent the child reading with understanding.

❖ **Total scoring:** the total score is the sum total of students' correct responses across all the subtasks. This indicates overall proficiency in English Literacy, Hindi literacy and numeracy skills.

Findings of Pilot Study

Task 1:- Reading with understanding

No. of words read	Understanding					
	100	80%	Understanding →		20%	0%
0-5	0	0	0	0	0	0
2-35	0	0	0	0	1	0
35-45	0	0	0	0	1	0
45-55	3	1	0	3	1	0
55-65	0	0	4	1	1	1
65-75	4	0	5	4	0	0

Figure No. 1

❖ The above graph is based on composite scoring. Composite benchmarking is being drawn based on the number of words read with 80% and more understanding. Four students are reading a paragraph of

65 words with 100% understanding. It means they can be independent readers, and they have learned the reading skills with complete understanding. Teachers can provide these students with reading

materials for self-learning or can take help these students with peer tutoring of students who are showing less understanding and ability to read fewer words. Two students reading with 20 % understanding can read only 25-45 words. Three students are reading 45-55 words with 100% understanding. One student is reading 45-55 words with 80% understanding. These students need to learn decoding techniques. One student is reading 55-65 words but with zero understanding. Nine students are reading 55-65 words with 40%-60% understanding. It means these students have learned the decoding technique but have to develop their understanding. The teacher can use dialogic reading techniques with them. So in this way, composite scores can be used to find out the differential needs of the students, and teachers can provide the intervention according to their need to close the learning gaps and develop their interest in lifelong learning.

- ❖ **Interpretation of task 1:-** Only eight students out of 30 are reading with at least 80% of understanding rest are mechanical readers. Average oral reading fluency is 57 words per minute, and the composite benchmark is 60 words per minute with 80 % understanding, and if we see the student reaching the required composite benchmark, it is only four students. Either they are slow readers, or they are reading with less understanding.
- ❖ This is being shown how teachers can identify the students learning needs by checking their sub-scores and composite scores. In the pilot study composite benchmark of reading with 80% and more

understanding for 3rd graders is 60 words per minute.

- ❖ According to the Australian national curriculum framework, a child is reading in class 3rd, and he must read 80 words per minute as he is eight years old. They calculate the number of words that should be read in a minute as age multiplied by 10 (age 10). English is a foreign language or second language.

Task 2 was assessed on the basis of a number of correct answers given to the questions based on shown advertisement. It assessed the students' observation, focus, and understanding of the visual.

Tasks 3 and 4 were meant to assess the listening power of the student. Task 3 was scored on the basis of a number of correct answers given after listening to the circular read by the teacher. Task 4 was assessed on the basis of a number of instructions followed correctly.

Task 5 assessed the art of writing on the basis of the shown picture. They were assessed on the basis of the accuracy of the spellings, punctuation, content, grammar and Cohesion.

Task 6 assessed the attentive listening of the children along with the accuracy of spelling. Students were scored on the basis of the accuracy of the spellings, punctuation and capitalization of the words.

Task 7 is based on students' knowledge and usage of silent words. They got a half mark for identifying the correct silent word and a half for correct pronunciation.

Tasks 8 and 9 assessed the spoken skills of the students.

Each task was scored separately, and the overall achievement of English literacy was drawn by adding the marks of all the tasks.

The overall achievement of English Literacy in grade 3

Figure No. 2

❖ The aforementioned graph represents the overall achievement of grade 3 in English in the pilot study. The average mark is 62 %. A total of 13 students are performing below the average proficiency level. The total overall achievement of English Literacy tells the overall proficiency level of the students. It does not pinpoint the weak areas of the students. Whereas figure number 1 clearly indicates subtask number 1, a number of words read per minute correctly. Subtask number 2 read the understanding level of the students. If students have answered all five questions correctly asked by the assessor from the passage read, it means the child is showing 100% understanding. When the composite score is taken into consideration, it showed clearly that ten students are mechanical readers; one student is able to read an entire paragraph correctly but with 0% understanding. So the assessor gets a clear picture of the child's performance, who is reading at the advanced level, who is a mechanical reader, and who is reading at the

strategic and intensive level. What kind of help can enhance their Reading with understanding.

The salient feature of the toolkit

This toolkit shifts the focus of assessment from marks to the description of the proficiency profile of the learner. Proficiency means students are able to apply the learnt skills in the classroom in real-life situations. The present toolkit does not check rote memorization, as it is not based on any prescribed textbook. Both reading comprehensions, given in the form of paragraphs and visuals, assess the foundational reading skills, cognitive processes and metacognitive competencies in an integrated manner.

The student has not had to sit for two-three hours alone and struggle to write the answers. The student's state of mind is taken into consideration by conducting rapport-building sessions. The assessor is able to assess the skill deficit along with carrying out the assessmentside by side. For instance, while assessing task 1, i.e. Reading. The assessor will note down the mistakes made by the child-like misspelt the word and making some addition or omission during Reading.

Difference between traditional tests and this toolkit

Traditional paper-pen tests are administered in groups. These tests are either norm-referenced tests, where the learners' performances are compared to the performance of other learners or sometimes, criteria-referenced tests. Learners' performances are evaluated against specific set standards. Students' results are expressed in the form of single-digit, which may tell the overall proficiency but fail to identify the learning gap of the students. They fail to know about their actual progress and fail to know about their teacher's expectations of them. They fail to establish new learning goals to keep them motivated. They get limited opportunities to improve their skills as once they receive grades or marks, they lose their motivation to learn. They make vertical up-gradation in their classes without making any learning progression. Learning progression is defined as the movement of learners from early knowledge, skills and understandings to more advanced knowledge, skills and understandings within the learning domain (Water, 2018)

Their grade increase but their proficiency decrease. So it is very crucial to change the assessment pattern.

This assessment toolkit is designed to identify the learning gaps in the area of Listening, Speaking, Reading, and writing. It does not simply assess whether the work is correct or incorrect. But also comments about the processes or strategies that support the task. It helps them to find out their place on the skill continuum and how to improve their position by knowing the strategies they can use to improve their own work. So it is not carried out to confer merits or declare them pass or fail. It is diagnostic in nature; its sole purpose is to identify the gaps and help the teachers to design interventions to remove these identified

learning gaps. It is not administered in groups but one on one basis.

Conclusion

This toolkit can be used for students studying in grade 3 in India. It can be used by the teachers, parents, and Pedagogical administrators who are interested to know the proficiency level in Foundational Skills in English Literacy for the students studying in grade 3. This toolkit will provide a clear-cut picture of the learning gaps of the students, which in turn would be helpful in designing differential instructions based on the differential needs of the students.

References

- ❖ ASER (2018): "Annual Status of Education Report flags poor learning outcomes in schools".
<https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.thehindu.com/news/national/aser-flags-poor-learning-outcomes-in-schools/article30569671.ece/amp/>
- ❖ Draft national education policy 2019. (Dr Kasturirangan Committee Report). New Delhi: Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India. Retrieved from [https://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Draft NEP 2019 EN Revised.pdf](https://mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/Draft%20NEP%202019%20EN%20Revised.pdf).
- ❖ Henderson, Anne T.; Mapp, Karen L. Catherine Snow, A New Wave of Evidence: The Impact of School, Family, and Community Connections on Student Achievement. Annual Synthesis, 2002.
- ❖ Kelly, T. L. (1939). Statistical methods in educational measurement. Journal of statistics and operational research. 9, 7-24.
- ❖ National Reading Panel (2000). Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on Reading and its implications for reading instruction. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Printing Office.

- ❖ Performance in Reading, Mathematics and Science, Figure 1.1, How proficient are students in Reading?
- ❖ RTI. (2009). Early Grade Reading Assessment Toolkit, Research Triangle Park, North Carolina: World Bank and USAID. OECD (2010), PISA 2009 Results, Volume I, What Students Know and Can Do: Student
- ❖ RTI International. (2009b). Early Grade Reading Assessment toolkit. Prepared for the World Bank, Office of Human Development, under Contract No. 7141961. Research Triangle Park, NC: Author. Retrieved from <https://www.eddataglobal.org/documents/index.cfm?fuseaction=pubDetail&ID=149>
- ❖ United States Agency for International Development (USAID). (2012). How-to note: Preparing evaluation reports. Monitoring and Evaluation Series, No. 1, Version 1.0. Washington, DC: USAID. Retrieved from <https://www.usaid.gov/sites/default/files/documents/1870/How-to-Note-Preparing-Evaluation-Reports.pdf>
- ❖ Sinha, S. (2012). Reading without meaning: the dilemma of Indian classrooms. Language and language teaching, 1 (1). 22-26. <http://llt.org.in/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/Language-Language-Teaching-Inaugural-Issue-pdf.io-6.pdf>.
- ❖ OECD. (2009). PISA 2009 Assessment Framework – Key competencies in Reading, mathematics and science. <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/pisaproducts/PISA%202009%20reading%20test%20items.pdf>
- ❖ Narasimhan, R. (2004). Characterizing Literacy. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- ❖ Matreja, G. (2006). Reading comprehension of English texts: A study of seventh, ninth, and eleventh-grade students [Unpublished

M. Ed. Dissertation, University of Delhi]. Delhi, India.

- ❖ Sinha, S. (1985). Exploring literature: An experience. Parents and Pedagogues, May-June. 3-4.

***UNESCO:- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization**

*** USAID:- United States Agency for International Development**

